

Innovative approach to lithium extraction: Integrating COOL+ Process with sustainable solid waste management

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21/6/2024

BACKGROUND OF SPODUMENE

Spodumene:

- Aluminosilicate of lithium ($\text{LiAlSi}_2\text{O}_6$)
- α -, β -, and γ -polymorphs
- Density $3,27 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$
- Mohs hardness of 6.5 to 7
- Thermal treatment of α -spodumene at $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours results in phase shift to β -spodumene
- The primary source (ore) of lithium
- Efficient extraction
- Important industrial application
- Sustainability

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the structure of α -spodumene (a), β -spodumene (b), and γ -spodumene (c)

Figure 2. Diagram of lithium usage

LIMITATIONS AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF LI EXTRACTION

SULFURIC ACID METHOD:

Table 1. Material consumption for 1t of produced lithium

Resources	Spodumene	H ₂ SO ₄	NaOH	Ca(OH) ₂	Na ₂ CO ₃	H ₂ O
Mass [t]	8,67	3,02	0,55	0,65	2,26	49,46

Table 2. The amount of pollutants per 1t of produced lithium

Pollutants	NO _x	SO ₂	H ₂ SO ₄	Waste
Mass [kg]	6,67	7,52	0,9	10 930

Lithium extraction intensity: 15,69 tCO_{2eq}/t

COST OF PRODUCTION

- Sulfuric method:
- If the price of spodumene concentrate is 1000 \$/t, the production cost of Li₂CO₃ exceeds 53 030 \$/t

INTRODUCTION TO THE COOL+ PROCESS

- COOL – supercritical **CO₂** Leaching in the liquid (H₂O) is an innovative method for recovering Li from both primary (spodumene) and secondary (black mass from spent Li-ion batteries) sources
- Developed by researchers at TU Bergakademie Freiberg (Germany)
- Efficient and environmentally friendly
- Aligns with the principles of the Circular Economy
- No additional precipitates are needed
- Zero-waste
- Objective: The goal of the COOL+ Process is to improve lithium recovery in an environmentally and economically acceptable way

STEP-BY-STEP BREAKDOWN OF THE COOL+ PROCESS

- Crushing and milling: $d_{90} = 65 \mu\text{m}$
- Thermal treatment: $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours
- Milling to a smaller particle size
- Leaching: 3 hours, 100 bar, $230 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
- Filtration – separating solid residue from the leaching solution
- Electrodialysis
- Li_2CO_3 precipitation
- Filtration and Li_2CO_3 extraction

Figure 3. Process flow of the COOL+ Process

RESULTS: QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE OUTCOMES

Figure 4. Optimization of the process by adjusting the percentage of added Na₂CO₃

- Highest Li recovery of 77 %:
- l/s ratio of 80, with 30 % of the solid content consisting of Na₂CO₃

Figure 5. Optimization of the process through analysis of the particle size distribution

- Highest Li recovery of 76 %:
- l/s ratio of 80, with 30 % of the solid content consisting of Na₂CO₃
- The difference in particle size distribution did not cause any major shifts in Li recovery

RESULTS: QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE OUTCOMES

Figure 6. Lithium recovery of the spodumene with the l/s ratio = 80 with 30 % of the solid content consisting of 20, 25, and 30 % of Na₂CO₃

- The content of the residue:
 - Nepheline – 85 %
 - Spodumene – 15 %

Figure 7. Optimization of the liquid-to-solid ratio (l/s) in the process

- The optimum l/s ratio of the Li extraction using the COOL+ Process is 80

ADVANTAGES OF THE COOL+ PROCESS

- Selective leaching of alkali metals
- Reduced consumption of chemicals
- No production of non-marketable sulfate salts
- No carbonate precipitation agents are required
- No Li losses due to precipitation
- Environmental impact: reduced ecological footprint
- Geopolymer production

COST-EFFECTIVENESS: ECONOMIC BENEFITS

Table 3. The COOL+ Process versus the adapted spodumene process

	Adapted spodumene process	The COOL+ Process
CAPEX [USD]	6 844 140	11 480 760
OPEX [USD]	12 526 243	7 953 729
<i>Low-price scenario</i>		
Dynamic amortization [years]	9.3	2.3
NPV (10a) [USD]	360 858	26 406 179
Cash flow [USD]	1 073 757	5 646 271
<i>High-price scenario</i>		
Dynamic amortization [years]	0.9	1.0
NVP (10a) [USD]	48 673 444	74 718 765
Cash flow [USD]	8 273 757	12 846 271

FUTURE PROSPECTS AND RESEARCH

Innovations:

- The development of more efficient sc-CO₂ systems to reduce costs and increase Li yield
- Full optimization of the process and possible automation
- Process engineering improvements to scale the COOL+ Process for larger industrial applications

Research:

- Investigating different lithium-bearing materials for the COOL+ Process
- Exploring advanced methods for recycling the by-products for the zero-waste principle
- Researching alternative reagents and process modifications to reduce operational costs

Collaborations:

- *Academic partnerships:* Collaboration with universities for cutting-edge research and innovation
- *Industrial partnerships:* Forming partnerships with the battery manufacturers and mining companies to implement the COOL+ Process on a commercial scale
- *Government grants:* Ensuring funding from governmental bodies to support R&D projects

SUMMARY

- Spodumene is the main ore for Li recovery
- Conventional Li recovery methods, such as the acid method, have a high environmental and financial impact
- The COOL+ Process is an innovative and effective Li recovery method from primary and secondary sources
- Solid residue as a by-product is not a waste but a resource for further processing – geopolymers
- The COOL+ Process provides 92 % of Li recovery
- Financially sustainable
- It allows further improvements and opens up the future perspective

Q&A

STAY IN CONTACT

Funded by
the European Union

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027) under grant agreement no 101091682

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